

Further record of *Sergia laminata* (Burkenroad, 1940) (Crustacea: Decapoda: Dendrobranchiata: Sergestidae) in western Mexico

Nuevo registro de *Sergia laminata* (Burkenroad, 1940) (Crustacea: Decapoda: Dendrobranchiata: Sergestidae) en el Pacífico mexicano

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ABSTRACT

The pelagic shrimp *Sergia laminata* is reported from off the west coast of the Baja California Peninsula, NW of Cedros Island. The single male specimen was identified based on the shape of the petasma. It is the second record of *S. laminata* for the Mexican Pacific. A list of recent changes in taxonomy of Sergestidae known to occur in western Mexico is provided.

Key words: Pelagic shrimp, eastern Pacific, California Current

RESUMEN

Se señala la presencia del camarón pelágico *Sergia laminata* frente a la costa oeste de la península de Baja California, al NO de isla Cedros. El único espécimen, un macho, fue identificado sobre la base de la forma del petasma. Representa el segundo registro de *S. laminata* para el Pacífico mexicano. Se presenta una lista de los cambios recientes en la taxonomía de los Sergestidae registrados en el Pacífico de México.

Palabras clave: Camarón pelágico, Pacífico Este, corriente de California

INTRODUCTION

The pelagic shrimps of western Mexico were reviewed by Hendrickx & Estrada Navarrete (1996) who recorded 53 species: 29 Dendrobranchiata and 24 Caridea. In this contribution, Sergestidae included three genera and 15 species: eight species each of *Sergestes*, six species of *Sergia*, and one species of *Petalidium* (Hendrickx & Estrada Navarrete 1996). Recent review of Sergestidae taxonomy, however, concluded that both *Sergestes* and *Sergia* needed to be split into several new genera: six in the case of *Sergestes* and seven in the case of *Sergia*

(Judkins & Kensley 2008; Vereshchaka et al. 2014). Consequently, the Sergestidae currently comprise 19 genera (WoRMS Editorial Board 2026) and the species of Sergestidae present in western Mexico are currently included in 10 genera instead of three (see Table 1).

Table 1. Names of species of Sergestidae included in Hendrickx & Estrada-Navarrete (1996) and currently recognized genera and species combinations. (1) currently recognized as junior synonyms; (2) originally included in *Sergestes*.

Hendrickx & Estrada Navarrete (1996)	Current name
<i>Sergestes consobrinus</i> Milne, 1968	<i>Neosergestes consobrinus</i> (Milne, 1968)
<i>Sergestes erectus</i> Burkenroad, 1940 (1)	<i>Deosergestes coalitus</i> (Burkenroad, 1940)
<i>Sergestes extensus</i> Hanamura, 1983 (1)	<i>Parasergestes armatus</i> (Kroyer, 1855)
<i>Sergestes halia</i> Faxon, 1893	<i>Parasergestes halia</i> (Faxon, 1893)
<i>Sergestes pectinatus</i> Sund, 1920	<i>Allosergestes pectinatus</i> (Sund, 1920)
<i>Sergestes pestafer</i> Burkenroad, 1937	<i>Allosergestes pestafer</i> (Burkenroad, 1937)
<i>Sergestes sargassi</i> Ortmann, 1893	<i>Allosergestes sargassi</i> (Ortmann, 1893)
<i>Sergestes similis</i> Hansen, 1903	<i>Eusergestes similis</i> (Hansen, 1903)
<i>Sergia bigemnea</i> (Burkenroad 1940) (2)	<i>Gardinerosergia bigemnea</i> (Burkenroad 1940)
<i>Sergia filicta</i> (Burkenroad, 1940) (2)	<i>Phorcosergia filicta</i> (Burkenroad, 1940)
<i>Sergia laminata</i> (Burkenroad, 1940) (2)	<i>Sergia laminata</i> (Burkenroad, 1940)
<i>Sergia maxima</i> (Burkenroad, 1940) (2)	<i>Phorcosergia maxima</i> (Burkenroad, 1940)
<i>Sergia phorca</i> (Faxon, 1893) (2)	<i>Phorcosergia phorca</i> (Faxon, 1893)
<i>Sergia scintillans</i> (Burkenroad, 1940) (2)	<i>Scintillosergia scintillans</i> (Burkenroad, 1940)
<i>Petalidium suspirosum</i> Burkenroad, 1937	<i>Petalidium suspirosum</i> Burkenroad, 1937

Of the 16 species reported by Hendrickx & Estrada Navarrete (1996) for western Mexico, only two have remained in the same genus: *Sergia laminata* (Burkenroad, 1940), originally described as a species of *Sergestes*, and *Petalidium suspirosum* Burkenroad, 1937. Additionally, two species included in Hendrickx & Estrada-Navarrete (1996) contribution are currently considered junior synonyms: *Sergestes erectus* Burkenroad, 1940, is a junior synonym of *Deosergestes coalitus* (Burkenroad, 1940), and *Sergestes extensus* Hanamura, 1983, is a junior synonym of *Parasergestes armatus* (Kroyer, 1855) (De Grave & Franssen 2011) (Table 1).

Sergia laminata was described as *Sergestes laminatus* based on material collected north of Madagascar, in the western Indian Ocean (Burkenroad 1940, De Grave & Franssen 2011). It is distributed throughout the tropical and subtropical Pacific and Atlantic Oceans, and in the western part of the Indian Ocean (Vereshchaka 2000: fig. 14). According to Hendrickx & Estrada Navarrete (1996: 70), there are only two previous records of this species in the East Pacific: San Pedro Basin (ca. 33°30'N 118°30'W, off southern California (Ebeling et al. 1970), and near Seamount 350, off the Baja California Peninsula (Hanamura 1983; 23°05'N 124°57'W) (Fig. 1). Krygier & Wasmer (1988: 50, table 1) reported this species in the "northeast Pacific", but they based their report on previous reports from Hawaii (Walters 1976), Japan (Hanamura 1979), and off Baja California (Hanamura 1983). A couple of years later, Vereshchaka (1990) recorded *S. laminata* above the Nazca and Salas-y-Gómez Ridge, off Chile. Vereshchaka (2000) provided an extensive synonymy for *S. laminata* and a distribution map that include two Dana stations, roughly off Ecuador, and a shaded area extending from central Chile to northern California (Vereshchaka 2000: fig. 14).

During an exploratory survey in western Mexico (TALUD Project), one male specimen of *Sergia laminata* was collected and represents the second record for this species off western Mexico. This material is reported herein.

Figure 1. Localities in the eastern Pacific where *Sergia laminata* (Burkenroad, 1940) has been recorded to date.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The unique specimen of *S. laminata* was collected during a deep-water exploratory survey off the west coast of the Baja California Peninsula, Mexico, the TALUD XVI cruise, aboard the R/V “El Puma”, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México (UNAM). The male specimen was collected during the ascent of a non-closing benthic sledge used to collect deep-water benthos (see Hendrickx 2024). Photographs of the petasma were obtained with a Canon Eos camera mounted on a Nikon SMZ-10A dissecting microscope. The specimen was deposited in the Regional Collection of Marine Invertebrates (ICML-EMU-catalogue number), at UNAM, in Mazatlán, Mexico. CL, carapace length.

RESULTS

Systematic section

Dendrobranchiata Spence Bate, 1888

Sergestidae Dana, 1852

Sergia Stimpson, 1860

Sergia laminata (Burkenroad, 1940)

Figs. 2, 3

Material examined. TALUD XVI, station 3 (28°39'N 115°49'W), July 31, 2013, off the Baja California Peninsula, one male, partly damaged (CL 11 mm), benthic sledge, between surface and 1397–1408 m depth (ICML-EMU-14122) (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. *Sergia laminata* (Burkenroad, 1940) (ICML-EMU-14122). Male (CL 11 mm). A, petasma, frontal view; B, same, caudal view. la, lobus accesorius; lc, lobus connectans; li, lobus inermis; lt, lobus terminalis; pu, processus uncinatus; pv, processus ventralis.

Unfortunately, Burkenroad (1940) did not provide illustrations of the type material of *S. laminata*. Illustrations of the carapace (lateral view), antennal scale (scaphocerite), flagellum of first antenna, uropodal appendages, and petasma of the holotype were provided by Vereshchaka (1994: figs. 5, 6) who examined the collection of material from the Dana Expedition. He noted small differences between this material from the Central Atlantic and the material reported by Kensley (1971: fig. 18) from southern Africa which he attributed to “geographical isolation”. The male specimen examined herein is damaged, missing the posterior part of the abdomen and part of the cephalic appendages. The petasma, however, is intact. The male specimen examined possesses a petasma very similar to these illustrated by Kensley (1971), reproduced by Hendrickx & Estrada Navarrete (1996: fig. 43C), and by Vereshchaka (1994). It is also similar to the petasma's illustration provided by Hanamura (1983: fig. 11f; specimen of 7.8 mm CL), also reproduced by Hendrickx & Navarrete (1996: 43D), and that corresponds to material from the eastern Pacific. Petasma's illustrations included in Hendrickx & Estrada Navarrete (1996: fig. 43C, D) contribution were also reproduced by Wicksten (2012). Vereshchaka (1994) did not cite Hanamura (1983) in his synonymy. Comparing the petasma of our material (Fig. 1) with these illustrations, particularly the petasma of the holotype, it seems reasonable to identify the material examined herein as *S. laminata*. All the illustrations available for this species feature a long, leaf-like processus ventralis (pv), overlapping both the lobus inermis (li) and the lobus connectans (lc), a long, curved lobus terminalis (lt) with a short li, a strongly curved lobus accesorius (la), and a short lc, not reaching the tip of the lt (Figs. 2, 3).

Figure 3. *Sergia laminata* (Burkenroad, 1940). A, B from Vereshchaka (1994: holotype); C, from Kensley (1971); D, from Hanamura (1983). Abbreviations as in figure 2.

Considering Hanamura (1983) record off the Baja California Peninsula, this is the second record of *Sergia laminata* for the Mexican Pacific and the first time a material of this species is included in the Regional Marine Invertebrate Collection, at UNAM in Mazatlán.

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